

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/10/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ~ 10.68	Bottom: ~ 10.53
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 18 cm	Width:	Length:	Depth: 15-0.17 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	CLAY	TAN to YELLOWISH	PACKED	FINE	T 0	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
		Al					
		Other					
1a	GYPSUM	BUFF TO YELLOW	PACKED	Rubby	T 0	Lm ✓ frags.	Gp
						Gr	Char ✓ Spots
					D	Do	
						Ba	
		Al					
		Other					
2	CLAY (?) - fine sand?	Lighter Tan-Brown to GREY	Packed	Fine to Powdery on Drying	T 3-4 plus minute particles ★	Lm ✓ small particles + few frags	Gp ✓ (?) Frag (1)
						Gr ✓ few small chips	Char ✓ Flecks and Particles
					D 0	Do kerite or ✓ few small chips 2-3	
						Basalt	
		Al					
		Other					
2a	Fine * sand clay? w/ gypsum mixed?	Light Greyish- Brown	Packed	Fine to slightly Rubby	T ✓	Lm ✓ Frags	Gp ✓ Flecks throughout ?
						Gr ✓	Char ✓ Spots
					D	Do	
						Ba	
		Al					
		Other					
2b	Fine sand- clay?	Greyish Brown **			T ✓	Lm ✓ Frags	Gp
						Gr ✓	Char ✓ small pieces
					D	Dolerite ✓ chips to 1x2 cm	
						Ba	
		Al					
		Other Yellow Clay Spots - w. seed remains "pods" impressions in clay					

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20 NE	Feature Plan: 1:10 Surface	Sections: 2 at 1:2	

REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: ★ minute pottery particles of bright red-orange ware
 * 2a under Flint cache - prob. same as 2
 ** Slightly darker than 2a - distinguishing feature yellow clay spots
 What distinguish fill 2 - 2b from fill of Fh16 2 - here def. brown color while
 2 Fh16 greyish.